

Analysis of the Role of Reverse Whole Brain Teaching Method in Foreign Language Learners with Aphasia Disorders

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ABSTRACT: People with Aphasia will have difficulty communicating with others, which will interfere with the learning process. The part that affects a person's speaking is the left brain. If the left brain is disturbed or damaged, it will make it difficult for individuals to speak. The Whole Brain teaching method teaches a learning method that does not only focus on one part of the brain. It is said that the human brain will work and function better if all parts of the brain are used. This paper examines using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). "The SLR method is a literature review method that identifies, examines, evaluates, and interprets all available research.... In this study, the collection of articles was carried out from Google Scholar, Research Gate, Sinta, DOAJ, and Scopus" (Hotmauli et al., 2024). 23 articles were related or closely related to the article's keywords: whole brain method, teaching, and learners with Aphasia disorders. Learners with aphasia disorders have damage to the left side; the whole brain method can teach from various aspects of the brain without having to rely on one side only. The whole brain method is a plus point and is needed for learners with this aphasia disorder.

KEYWORDS: Aphasia, Learning, Neurolinguistics, Systematic Literature Review (SLR), Whole Brain Method.

INTRODUCTION

"Language disorders are a condition of difficulty speaking or communicating by an individual who has a brain dysfunction" (Nabilah et al., 2024). Experiencing language disorders can interfere with conveying something to others. Generally, language disorders are caused by brain damage or diseases that attack the human brain. One term to describe language disorders due to brain damage is called Aphasia. "Aphasia is a communication disorder caused by damage to the part of the brain that contains language (usually in the left cerebral hemisphere of the brain, which is the more dominant brain)" (Nurfadhillah et al., 2021).

The part that affects a person when speaking is the left brain, the dominant part of the human brain, which is the left side. People who experience Aphasia will have difficulty communicating with others, which may interfere with the learning process. "Aphasia is a disorder that interferes with language skills, making learning, understanding, and speaking difficult" (Anas et al., 2024).

The left brain not only contains language but also understands something. In addition to having difficulty communicating and speaking, someone who has difficulty understanding is caused by damage to the left brain. Generally, damage to the left side is caused by a stroke or having seizures as a child due to a high fever and not being treated immediately. "It can be concluded that aphasia (aphasia) is a disorder that attacks the brain in the language acquisition section as a result of an accident or disease that attacks the brain so that the brain does not receive signals which cause the brain's work in the language section not to be optimal" (Meili et al., 2024).

"The basic idea behind Whole Brain Teaching is that the human brain is more effective in learning when all parts of the brain are involved, rather than using only one part of the brain" (Maola et al., 2024). The Whole Brain teaching method teaches a learning method that does not only focus on one part of the brain. The human brain will work and function better if all parts of the brain are used. In applying learning methods, learners will be more effective if they are taught a method that uses all parts of the brain.

This paper examines how the relationship between use of the Whole Brain method affects or impacts foreign language learners with Aphasia disorders. This paper also analyzes the findings of studies on the Whole Brain method in teaching and whether it can correlate if the learner has Aphasia disorder.

METHODOLOGY

This paper examines the topic above by reviewing existing literature related to the topic raised. Usually called a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). "The SLR is a literature review method that identifies, reviews, evaluates, and interprets all available research... In

this study, the collection of articles was carried out from Google Scholar, Research Gate, Sinta, DOAJ, and Scopus" (Hotmauli et al., 2024).

The use of this method is to review, search for, and understand research related to the paper's topic. This paper collects related articles from all existing publication search engines, such as Google Scholar, DOAJ, Sinta, Scopus, and Research Gate. The articles collected are articles from 1999 to 2024. Twenty-three articles relate to the topic of this paper, then divide into two groups: Whole Brain Model in learning and teaching and learners with Aphasia disorders.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Result

a) Whole Brain Model on learning and teaching

No	Research title and researcher	Sample	Method	Result
1	The Whole Brain Creativity Model: Implications for Nursing Education and Practice (Potgieter, 1999)	Articles	Literary review	whole brain teaching and learning The model can help nurse educators to apply a holistic approach to teaching. Discussion: By utilizing a variety of teaching strategies, nurse educators can stimulate all four quadrants of the nursing student's brain
2	Penerapan Pendekatan Accelerated Learning Dengan Metode Whole Brain Teaching Dalam Pembelajaran Fisika Di Smp (Albab & Astutik, 2012)	VII (Seventh) grade students in Junior High School 3 Jember consist of 6 classes such as VII-A, VII-B, VII-C, VII-D, VII-E, dan VII-F, school year 2011/2012	Experimental	The application of the accelerated learning approach with the whole brain teaching method in physics learning has been proven to make students happy, enthusiastic, active, and able to improve students' social skills during learning.
3	Pengembangan Perangkat Pembelajaran Matematika Berkarakter Berdasarkan Whole Brain Teaching Pokok Bahasan Bangun Ruang Sisi Lengkung Kelas Ix Smp (Tri et al., 2013)	Syllabus, lesson implementation plan, student books, student worksheets, and learning outcome tests	Research and Development	Based on the results of data analysis, a character-based mathematics learning device was produced based on whole-brain teaching on curved-sided spatial structures that met the criteria of validity, practicality, and effectiveness.
4	Peran Neurolinguistik dalam Pengajaran Bahasa (Budianingsih, 2015)	Books, journal papers, articles, dissertations, theses, handouts, laboratory manuals, and scientific works	Library study or literature study	The process of acquiring language skills supports communication skills. This language deficiency is only a language disorder or delay that exceeds the golden period of language acquisition.

5	In Pursuit Of A 'Whole Brain' Approach To Undergraduate Teaching: Implications Of The Herrmann Brain Dominance Model (Hughes et al., 2016)	414 respondents	Quantitative (questionnaire and survey)	A 'whole brain' approach is possible. However, it depends on the strategic design of the teaching methods incorporated into courses and modules rather than simply a random selection of activities.
6	A Whole Brain® learning approach to an undergraduate auditing initiative – an exploratory study (Kirstein & Kunz, 2016)	Books, journal papers, articles, dissertations, theses, handouts, laboratory manuals, and scientific works	Library research or literature study.	Case study teaching can accommodate the flexibility of learning styles when measured against Herrmann's Whole Brain® Model
7	Model brain-based learning (BBL) and whole-brain teaching (WBT) in learning (Handayani & Corebima, 2017)	Books, journal papers, articles, dissertations, theses, handouts, laboratory manuals, and scientific works	Library research or literature study.	<p>(1) The brain's natural learning system is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the nerves in each hemisphere do not work independently, (b) the more activities are done, the more brain nerves are connected, (c) the right hemisphere controls the motor sensors of the left side of the body, and vice versa; <p>(2) The characteristics of BBL and WBT are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) BBL is based on the structure and function of the brain, while the WBT model is based on an instructional approach, neurolinguistics, and body language, (b) The parts of the brain that work in BBL are the cerebellum, cerebral cortex, frontal lobe, limbic system, and prefrontal cortex, while the parts that work in WBT are the prefrontal cortex, visual cortex, motor cortex, limbic system, and amygdala, (c) The similarities between the two are that they rely on the brain system and support gestures in learning, while the differences lie in the views on the purpose of gestures and the learning theories on which they are based. BBL is based on cognitive theory, while WBT is based on social theory; <p>(3) the</p>

				characteristic of both compared to other models is that in BBL, there is classical music and gestures in the form of easy exercises, while in the WBT model, there are instructions and fast movements as instructions or codes for each word spoken.
8	The Effects of the 4MAT Teaching Model and Whole Brain Model on Academic Achievement in Science (Tezcan & Güvenç, 2017)	68 students in Sixth grade	Quantitative, static group pre-test and post-test design	It was found that the three learning methods applied could improve science learning achievement. In addition, it was found that the 4MAT Learning Model was more effective than the Whole Brain Model in improving learning achievement.
9	The Influence Of Implementation Brain-Friendly Learning Through The Whole Brain Teaching To Students' Response And Creative Character In Learning Mathematics (Winarso & Karimah, 2017)	36 students of Junior High School 4 Palimanan, Cirebon	Quantitative (questionnaire)	The implementation of brain-friendly learning through Whole Brain Teaching has a positive influence on students' creative character in mathematics learning.
10	Improving Students' Science Learning Achievement By Using "Whole Brain Teaching" Method In Human Blood Circulate System (A Classroom Action Research at Fifth Grade of MI Al Istiqomah in the Academic Year of 2016/2017) (Christian, 2018)	Fifth-grade students MI Al Istiqomah, Musi Rawas Utara	Classroom Action Method	Applying the Whole Brain Teaching method in science subjects can improve the learning achievement of class V students at MI Al Istiqomah, Nibung District, North Musi Rawas Regency.
11	The Relation Between Learning Styles according to the Whole Brain Model and Emotional Intelligence: A Study	Eight hundred fifty-three college students were respondents from three faculties.	Quantitative	Learning styles based on mixed dominance have a positive effect on the development of emotional intelligence. Learning styles associated with the brain's right hemisphere have also significantly impacted emotional intelligence.

	of University Students (Estrada et al., 2019)			
12	Mathematics Critical Thinking Ability Based on Student's Cognitive Style in Whole Brain Teaching in Ethnomathematics (Rahayu et al., 2019)	XII (seventh) grade students Senior High School 2 Grabag Magelang Odd semester, school year 2018/2019	Mixed method	(1) The Whole Brain Teaching learning model in ethnomathematics is effective and (2) The critical mathematical thinking ability of each group, from six indicators of critical mathematical thinking ability, FD students are capable and expert in three indicators, FIL students are capable and expert in four indicators, and FIK students are capable and master all indicators.
13	Keterampilan Berpikir Kritis: Model Brain-Based Learning Dan Dan Model Whole Brain Teaching (Shaleha et al., 2019)	V (fifth) grade Elementary school 3 Senggeng Kecamatan Sumberpucung	Pre-Experimental quantitative	Critical thinking skills using the Whole Brain Teaching model are higher than in the Brain-Based Learning model.
14	The Use of Whole Brain Teaching Method in Improving Students' Speaking Ability (Devana, 2020)	X (tenth) students of Public Vocational High School 2 OKU school year 2020/2021	pre-experimental using pre-test and post-test methods	Applying the Whole Brain Teaching method in speaking learning for class X students of SMK Negeri 2 OKU has positively influenced and contributed to students' speaking skill achievements.
15	Keefektifan Model Pembelajaran Berbasis Otak Dalam Pembelajaran Menulis Paragraf Argumentatif Di Sman 1 Sindang Kabupaten Indramayu (Kohar, 2021)	Students of Public Senior High School 1 Sindang Indramayu	quasi-experimental with One-Group design; Pretest-Posttest Design	Brain-based learning model proven effective in learning to write argumentative paragraphs at SMAN 1 Sidang Indramayu
16	Beyond left and right: learning is a whole-brain process (Shin et al., 2022)	Books, journal papers, articles, dissertations, theses, handouts, laboratory manuals, and scientific works	Library research or literature study.	Brain-based learning model proven effective in learning to write argumentative paragraphs at SMAN 1 Sidang Indramayu
17	The Effect of Applying the Whole Brain Teaching (WBT) Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Social Science	IV(sixth) class MIN Lubuk Buaya Padang	Quantitative-quasi-experimental	There is a significant influence between the learning outcomes of students who apply the Whole Brain Teaching strategy and those who apply the conventional learning model in the social studies subject of class IV MIN Lubuk Buaya Padang.

	Subjects (IPS) Class IV MIN Lubuk Buaya Padang (Rizki Mulyani & Mahaputra, 2023)			
18	Penerapan Metode Whole Brain Teaching untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Berbicara Siswa (Maola et al., 2024)	Books, journal papers, articles, dissertations, theses, handouts, laboratory manuals, and scientific works	Literary review	Whole-brain teaching can improve students' speaking skills

b) Learners with Aphasia Disorders

No	Research title and researcher	Sample	Method	Result
1	Ekspresi Verbal-Gramatikal Penyandang Afasia Broca Berbahasa Indonesia: Suatu Kajian Neurolinguistik (Nasrullah et al., 2020)	3 (three) respondents	Qualitative	The first respondent succeeded in producing 162 speech constructions based on the topic of conversation, the second respondent succeeded in producing 56 speech constructions based on the topic of conversation, and the third respondent succeeded in producing 64 speech constructions based on the topic of conversation.
2	Advancing Neurolinguistics in Russia: Experience and Implications of Building Experimental Research and Evidence-Based Practices (Ivanova et al., 2021)	Books, journal papers, articles, dissertations, theses, handouts, laboratory manuals, and scientific works	Literary review	Some practical aspects of developing new research, clinical, and educational programs. On the funding side, it is important to ensure stability so that staff can continue working on projects while continuing to develop professionally. Building a network of collaborating clinical sites is another significant vector of development. Access to different clinical resources and patient populations is key to productive neuroscience research.
3	Analisis Pembelajaran Anak Aphasia Dan Diskalkulia Pada Siswa Kelas 4 Di Sd Negeri Tegal Alur 02 Pagi (Nurfadhillah et al., 2021)	IV (sixth) grade teachers in Public Elementary School 02 Tegal Alur.	Qualitative with survey	The test results show that the percentage of answers that are most often wrong is the answer.
4	Gangguan Berbahasa Afasia	X (tenth) grade students Vocational	Qualitative with descriptive design	Students' utterances containing Broca's Aphasia can occur, namely, because they

	Broca Dalam Pembelajaran Debat Pada Siswa Kelas X Smk (Yusat et al., 2023)	High School of Fahd Islamic School		are entangled when pronouncing a word, are in a hurry to finish speaking, cannot compose words grammatically, and lack mastery of the material of the motion obtained
5	Relasi Bahasa Dan Otak serta Gangguan Berbahasa dalam Pembelajaran Bahasa Arab (Nabilah et al., 2024)	Books, journals and scientific articles	Literary review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The relationship between language and the brain is that the human organ that is responsible for controlling and coordinating all movements and functions of the body, including language, is the brain. • Language disorders are a condition of difficulty speaking or communicating by an individual with a brain dysfunction. • Causes of language disorders include delays in language development and Aphasia. Aphasia can be grouped into several types, including sensory Aphasia, motor aphasia, conductive Aphasia, and amnesic Aphasia. Language disorders can also be seen from a biological and cognitive perspective. • A disorder in the area of the brain involved in understanding language can inhibit a person's ability to understand and express sentences in Arabic.

From the articles collected, 23 articles related to the keywords of the article's topic, namely, whole brain model, teaching, and learners with Aphasia disorders. These articles analyze the topic of this article. The analysis will outline facts regarding the role of the whole brain method in teaching, which will later be intended for Aphasia learners.

2. Language Disorder: Aphasia

The brain plays an important role in a person's language acquisition. However, in reality, a person's language ability will decrease with age when brain function degrades, or specific events cause damage to the brain.

"The brain is a vital area in language acquisition, the process of understanding and language use. The ability of humans who have mastered language can sometimes disappear from human mastery itself or can be said to be "might not ever long-lasting", which is caused by damage to the human brain itself" (Sarifuddin, 2023). "Language disorders divide into two—first, medical factor disorders; and second, due to environmental factors.

What medical factors mean are disorders either due to brain function or abnormalities in the speech organs. It means social and environmental factors is the unnatural human living environment, such as being marginalized or isolated from the typical human social environment (Chaer, 2003, p. 148) (Sanjaya, 2015).

Language disorders divide into two: one due to medical factors, generally described as a disorder in brain function or speech organs. Second, due to the environment where the individual has had bad experiences in the past, such as being marginalized or ostracized, which results in psychological disorders that make the individual not have the courage to speak.

"Speech aphasia disorders in someone who has a stroke" states that to speak, the muscles regulate the speech organs such as the tongue and jaw. Nerves will regulate every important muscle for communication and connect to the brain area" (Novita & Kuntarto, 2020). "If a stroke attacks the left brain and affects the speech center, the patient is likely to experience speech disorders or aphasia (Mulyatsih, 2008, p.36)" (Suharti et al., 2016).

When someone has a stroke, it may attack the left brain, which will eventually cause the person to experience speech disorders. A stroke in the left brain will cause difficulty in speaking because the movement of the tongue, jaw, and all the muscles used in communication are related to the brain. That is why the left brain regulates a person's ability to speak, understand speech, and communicate with others.

"People with aphasia may have problems in speaking, reading, writing and language comprehension" (Alons et al., 2017). That is why, in general, people with Aphasia generally have difficulty communicating, reading, writing, and understanding speech. However, not all aphasia sufferers experience all of these things, depending on the type of Aphasia they suffer from.

Those with Aphasia tend to be the subject of ridicule and bullying in today's society. "Individuals with aphasia are often marginalized, labeled by their condition, and made invisible by their assumed inability to communicate (Dalemans, Wade, van den Heuvel, & de Witte, 2009)" (Doherty & Lay, 2019).

"Research conducted by Ferina, Ardhyantama, and Fath (2020) in grade 3 of SD Negeri 1 Hadiluwih experienced difficulty speaking during learning; there were several children who faced difficulty speaking, this difficulty causes by several reasons from outside and from within the students, students who had difficulty speaking got less than optimal learning outcomes" (Fauzi et al., 2023).

Aphasia can also occur due to treatment received from the environment. Maybe initially, the individual did not dare to say what he wanted to say. However, due to the ridicule he received, the lack of courage became worse and caused the individual to experience Aphasia. The article by Ardhyantama and Fath, quoted by Fauzi et al., stated that language difficulties can be caused from within or outside the learner. This means that pressure or ridicule received can make the disorder worse.

3. Types of Aphasia

There are two types of Aphasia: Wernicke's Aphasia and Broca's Aphasia. "People with fluent Aphasia or Wernicke's Aphasia can, at first glance, pronounce a sentence or words well. However, observing closely will show that the speech, words, or sentences produced feel odd (abnormal). People with Wernicke's Aphasia can produce language and speech fluently, but logically, the meaning is different from what it should be" (Dewi, 2020). "Damage to the "Wernicke's area" may result in reduced ability to understand speech, although the ability to speak is relatively not affected" (Nasrullah et al., 2019).

Wernicke's Aphasia is related to fluency in speech. A person who suffers from this type of Aphasia can still speak and communicate with good and fluent language, but only in terms of meaning; some of it does not match what is meant. "Broca's aphasia is also called expressive aphasia, defined as a symptom caused by damage to the third part of the anterior circle of the left dominant hemisphere of the brain or to the motor cortex that maintains the speech muscles (Sastra, 2011: 43)" (Nasrullah et al., 2020).

"Damage to "Broca's area" may result in reduced speaking ability, even though the comprehension ability is rather undisturbed" (Nasrullah et al., 2019). In damage to Broca's area, a person will have difficulty speaking; it will be challenging to say something. Unlike Wernicke, who is disturbed by understanding meaning, Broca can still understand speech well.

4. Whole Brain Method

Herrmann created the whole brain method in his article in 1998. De Boer et al.'s research stated that a teacher who can understand the whole brain method can help improve students' intelligence. "Becoming a whole brain® intelligent lecturer makes fertile soil for cultivating and nourishing intelligence in higher education" (De Boer et al., 2015).

From the research of De Boer et al., it is stated that the use of the whole brain method can improve types of intelligence. "Ultimately we claim that activating whole brain® innovation to nourish multiple intelligences is only a particle of the higher education cosmos" (De Boer et al., 2015).

The learning and teaching process regarding the whole brain method understands the function of all quadrants of the brain and how to learn from the various quadrants. "Based on our research and by extending the Herrmann (1995) model, a comprehensive whole-

brain model was designed (De Boer et al., 2013). This metaphorical model represents the four quadrants (A, B, C, and D) Herrmann (1995) identified.

Figure 1. Whole Brain model De Boer et al (De Boer et al., 2015)

The A quadrant focuses on logical, rational, quantitative, and theoretical thinking (What?). B quadrant thinking entails organizing and sequential and methodological approaches to executing tasks (How?). The C quadrant focuses on emotional, expressive, interpersonal, and kinetic aspects of emotive thinking (Who?). D quadrant thinking is about visual, experimental, simultaneous, and conceptual thinking (Why?)" (De Boer et al., 2015).

Part A is related to human logic, which is also related to calculations or mathematical abilities, and is also related to theoretical thinking, which is generally related to the question, what? Part B is related to the human ability to organize and organize something. This part is also related to how humans think to analyze something related to the method or procedure and is described in the question how?

Part C is the part of the human brain that regulates a person's emotional side and how to express something. This part is also related to kinesthetic, a person's learning style in learning something that involves physical movement, touching, or experiencing an event. Described in the question who? Part D is related to a person's ability to visualize something and describe what is in their mind. Part D is related to a person's critical thinking and creativity.

The description of part D is in the form of the question why? That is why when a teacher can activate all parts of his brain in teaching and teaching his students this learning method, De Boer et al. confirmed from their research that it can increase intelligence from various aspects: logical aspects, procedural aspects, kinesthetic aspects, and kinesthetic aspects.

The whole brain method is not only for learning methods but can also be for measuring a person's addiction to something by measuring the emotional habits that arise from game players. "Therefore, the causal model of the relationship between addiction to online games, brain lateralization, and behavioral regulation of emotion was confirmed based on various fit indices" (Atadokht & Ebadi, 2023). The results of this study illustrate that the relationship between online game addiction, brain lateralization, and behavioral regulation of emotions is confirmed based on various fit indices. People addicted to online games will be depicted from emotional behavior. The whole-brain method can also help teachers become better professionals.

"What we have found thus far is that caveats in the literature regarding studies on Whole Brain® action research do exist. No studies on Whole Brain® lecturer identity formation exist. This allows us to construct a new meaning of lecturer identity formation and action research and participatory action research – to contribute to scholarship advancement of the professional development of early-career academics in health sciences as a scholarly niche. This is what we are aiming at as a scholarly community of practice" (Du Toit, 2022).

The new whole brain method limits in helping teaching and learning, which will help students better understand the logical, procedural, and kinesthetic aspects. However, there is nothing related to the teacher himself. The purpose of Du Toit's research is to form lecturer identity and action research and participatory action research, and it also contributes to the professional development of academics.

CONCLUSION

Learners with language disorders such as Aphasia need different learning methods. It will be difficult for these learners to use conventional teaching methods because of their limitations in understanding language, communicating and speaking. The whole brain method activates understanding and intelligence from various abilities from each part of the brain. Learners with Aphasia have damage to the left side; the whole brain method can teach from various aspects of the brain without having to rely on one side only but requires adjustment. The studies above show that the whole brain method is a plus as a method needed for learners with this aphasia disorder but there must be adjustments in order to overcome the disorder.

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